

POLICY BRIEF

A Fresh Approach for Digital Skills Testing Needed

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Policy Brief

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1. Introduction

Everything nowadays is digital. We want children and young people to be digitally skilled. But their digital skills are unequally distributed and this is not without consequences. Therefore, digital inclusion is crucial. We need skill indicators for individuals as well as success indicators in order to generate a collective impact. However, there is an **underdevelopment of measures** for testing the softer non-technical skills that allow young people to interact in a civil manner on social media.

In ySKILLS we understand **digital skills as a diverse set of operational, information navigation, communicative, creative and mobile competences**, which are unequally distributed and influenced by a number of individual and contextual variables. Such a choice obviously has repercussions for the policy to be followed.

One research objective of ySKILLS is to acquire extensive knowledge and **better measurement of digital skills** in order to build evidence-based policy.

Another objective of ySKILLS is to **explain the uneven distribution of digital skills through a model** that identifies the **actors and factors and the pathways** that lead to the acquisition of digital skills.

Figure 1: the ySKILLS model

2. Evidence and Analysis

In the first year of ySKILLS' work, we conducted a [systematic evidence review](#) to investigate **which concepts/variables are important for digital skills**. Few studies were identified that examined whether digital skills improve wellbeing, and even fewer found that they do. There is a clearer evidence that greater digital skills are linked to **better learning outcomes** for children. Of the few studies that looked for a relationship between digital skills and **youth civic engagement** (offline and online), all found it to be positive. Children with higher levels of digital skills may be better able to protect their **privacy online**.

In order to make statements on concepts that are important for digital skills **from a cross-cultural European perspective**, we carried out a [secondary analysis](#) of the 2020 EUKIDS Online dataset, which examines children's online activities both in depth and breadth but investigates only **self-reported skills**.

On the **antecedents** of digital skills, the secondary analysis shows us that:

- **Age** has a positive influence on digital skills.
- The role of **SES** is only indirect, mediated by access to devices.
- There is **no clear-cut North-South digital divide** in Europe, and there are only **small to medium differences** across countries as to children's **claimed digital skills**.
- The more online activities children engage in, the **more opportunities** for digital skills development, though cultural differences exist.
- The influence of **parental mediation** on digital skills is small and indirect via online opportunities being facilitated.
- **Restrictive mediation** negatively predicts online activities, be it communication, entertainment or education.
- **Feeling safe online** is a positive predictor in almost all European countries: the higher the familiarity with the digital environment, the better the knowledge and understanding of the internet and digital technologies.

On the **consequences of digital skills**, the secondary analysis taught us that:

- Our information digital skills are related to **information-seeking** activities.
- Social digital skills are not significant predictors of social digital activities.
- Higher levels of digital skills are associated with **more exposure to harmful digital content**.
- The more digitally skilled children who explore the internet to a great extent may be more likely to encounter **online risks**.
- However, digital skills **prevent** these risks from translating into harm.
- Digital skills also **mitigate** the relationship between emotional problems and exposure to harmful online content.
- Children with emotional problems who are digitally skilled are more likely to be exposed to harmful online content but less likely to be negatively affected by it.

3. Policy Implications and Recommendations: A plea for more coherence

From our [interviews](#) and a [webinar](#) with experts in education and the labour market, we learned that the current quality and effectiveness of initiatives intended to build digital skills are **often deficient and inconsistent**, and vary greatly within and across countries. This confirms the **need for more coherence**, not least in policy.

A crucial question at the level of policymaking is to find an adequate response to the following question:

how can the current fragmented approach to digital literacy in the European member states be turned into a more efficient and sustainable policy framework that takes into account individual vulnerabilities as well as a life-span perspective?

Source: D2.1, Haddon et al., 2020

Figure 2: antecedents and consequences of digital skills

The development of digital skills and the promotion of digital literacy are **not tasks that only concern the formal education system**. Digital skills development requires the **involvement of all**, including citizens themselves from young to old, but also the **public and the private sector**, where the perceived ‘value’ in economic terms of investing in digital skills in a lifelong learning trajectory varies greatly from sector to sector.

Looking at **formal education** in particular, one of the most important challenges is to bring teachers into line with the needs of the digital society. The COVID-19 crisis has taught us that distance learning must be further developed. The focus should be on **pooling good practices**. Communities of practice where knowledge is produced and practices are shared among teachers through social and digital media platforms are a possible factor of success.

The pandemic made it also clear how important the **supporting role of the teacher** and the **socialising role of the school** are. High quality distance learning depends on the availability of digital tools and skills.

The example of **Italy** where teachers are given an individual budget to train themselves (‘micro learning’) seems to be a good practice that merits replication. The **Finnish** model is also inspirational as media and digital literacy are transversal objectives embedded in the curriculum, independent of whether the subject is history, mathematics or language, or whether the teacher is able or ready to use digital resources.

From a **labour market perspective**, while technical and problem-solving or critical skills are considered important, **CEO’s of top German companies** favour social, collaboration and self-

management skills the most, although the latter are currently perceived as seriously underdeveloped. Moreover, children and young people do not acquire these skills in formal education only.

This finding bears careful investigation, especially since digital citizenship, active participation in democracy and society will also demand the development of skills which may not seem as relevant for all or certain labour market sectors.

Hence, it is important to consider how to **support digital skills education after school**, seen from a **lifespan perspective**, especially for groups who do not have access to regular training opportunities at work, or who have not (yet) achieved desirable levels of media and digital literacy during formal education.

Good policy is evidence-based. We recommend the **monitoring of digital skills** among children and young people to gain insight into the presence or absence of digital skills in order to adjust policy accordingly, and the **evaluation of initiatives** that aim to promote digital skills.

The **development of measuring instruments** (e.g. [The Youth Digital Skills Indicator](#) or yDSI) is paramount to monitor on a regular basis the digital skills of children and young people. This instrument will be used as part of the ySKILLS school surveys (second round) in six countries (Estonia, Finland, Germany, Italy, Poland, and Portugal) in 2022. Ideally, such an instrument, which will allow us to directly assess children's digital skills in performing tasks in relation to what they themselves claim they know and are able to do, should be implemented in all EU Member States. The media, information and digital literacy organisations are the most appropriate partners for this.

4. Project Identity

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- Funding programme: RIA - Research and Innovation action
- Duration: January 2020 – December 2023 (48 months).
- Website: www.ySKILLS.eu.
- Social Media:

ySKILLS Partners

The ySKILLS consortium includes 15 partners who will actively engage in meeting the objectives of the project. To achieve these objectives, ySKILLS brings together leading international centres for research on media studies, communication sciences, youth research, psychology, pedagogy, law, educational neuroscience and sociology.

